

The Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Antimicrobial Resistance among Blood Culture Isolates in a Tertiary Care Hospital at North India

Nagendra Kumar¹, Vanshika Sharma², Komal Tanwar³, Rauhana Qadri⁴, Sandeep Dogra⁵

^{1,2,3}PG Student, PG Department of Microbiology, GMC, Jammu

⁴Lecturer, PG Department of Microbiology, GMC, Jammu

⁵Professor and Head, PG Department of Microbiology, GMC, Jammu

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Nagendra Kumar

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Abstract:

Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on healthcare systems worldwide, including the management of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in hospital settings. Previous research has highlighted the challenges faced by hospitals in India during the pandemic, such as weak infrastructure, inadequate infection control measures, and financial constraints that have affected patient safety and overall hospital performance. This study aims to investigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance among blood culture isolates in a tertiary care hospital in North India.

Aim and Objective: This study aims to investigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance among blood culture isolates in a tertiary care hospital in North India during pre-covid, pandemic period and post pandemic period. To determine the trends in antimicrobial resistance patterns among blood culture isolates in a tertiary care hospital in North India during the COVID-19 pandemic period.

Materials and Methods: This retrospective study analyzed data on blood culture isolates collected from patients admitted to the hospital during the study period from July 2019 to December 2023. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method, and the results were interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines and NCDC, New Delhi. NCDC resistance patterns were used.

Results: The results of the study will provide insights into the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance patterns among blood culture isolates in the tertiary care hospital. The data will be analyzed to identify any significant changes in the prevalence of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens during the pandemic period compared to the pre-pandemic, pandemic and post-pandemic periods. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the understanding of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance in a hospital setting in North India, which can inform future strategies for managing antimicrobial resistance and improving patient safety during public health emergencies.

Conclusions: The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on healthcare systems worldwide, including the management of antimicrobial resistance in hospital settings. This study aims to investigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance among blood culture isolates in a tertiary care hospital in North India. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the understanding of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance in a hospital setting in North India, which can inform future strategies for managing antimicrobial resistance and improving patient safety during public health emergencies.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Antimicrobial Resistance, Multidrug Resistant Bacteria, Hospital Infection Surveillance, Antibiotic Stewardship.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on healthcare systems worldwide, including the management of antimicrobial resistance in hospital settings. Previous research has highlighted the challenges faced by hospitals in India during the pandemic, such as weak infrastructure, inadequate

infection control measures, and financial constraints that have affected patient safety and overall hospital performance (Wang & Wang, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic has also had an impact on the provision of essential healthcare services, including routine childhood immunization (Khan et al.,

2021). The diversion of resources towards the management of COVID-19 patients has resulted in disruptions to regular healthcare services, which may have indirect consequences on antimicrobial resistance patterns.

In this context, it is crucial to understand the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance among blood culture isolates in a tertiary care hospital in North India. This study aims to investigate the trends in antimicrobial resistance patterns among blood culture isolates during the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic periods. This retrospective study analyzed data on blood culture isolates collected from patients admitted to the hospital during the study period of July 2019 to December 2023, with antimicrobial susceptibility testing performed using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method and interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines and NCDC, New Delhi. The findings of this study are expected to contribute to the understanding of the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance in a hospital setting in North India, which can inform future strategies for managing antimicrobial resistance an improving patient safety during public health emergencies.

Material and Methods

This retrospective study analyzed data on blood culture isolates collected from patients admitted to a tertiary care hospital in North India during the study period from July 2019 to December 2023. The antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method, and the results were interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines and NCDC, New Delhi (Arentz et al., 2022). The study included blood culture isolates from patients with both community-acquired and healthcare-associated infections.

The study was performed a comparative analysis of the antimicrobial resistance patterns observed among the blood culture isolates during the pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic periods to identify any significant changes in the prevalence of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens. Data collected from the hospital's microbiology laboratory will be used for this analysis. To assess the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance, the study will compare the resistance patterns of the following key pathogens: *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus spp.* and *Acinetobacter baumannii* as per NCDC, New Delhi data. Data entry by whonet 2023 software. (Bogdan et al., 2023)(Sands et al., 2023)(Papamanoli et al., 2020)

Results

The on-going COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the landscape of antimicrobial resistance, particularly among the ESKAPE pathogens, which are known for their ability to evade the effects of commonly used antibiotics (Pandey et al., 2021) (Qian et al., 2023) (Hang et al., 2022) (Santos et al., 2022). These pathogens, including *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter spp.*, have become increasingly problematic in healthcare settings, posing a serious threat to patient safety and outcomes (Hang et al., 2022)(Qian et al., 2023) (Pandey et al., 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic had led to an increase in the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, often used empirically to treat suspected bacterial co-infections in COVID-19 patients (Rosa et al., 2020). This indiscriminate use of antibiotics has further exacerbated the problem of antimicrobial resistance, as it has provided a selective pressure for the emergence and spread of resistant strains of these ESKAPE pathogens (Rosa et al., 2020) (Qian et al., 2023).

Moreover, the disruption of healthcare services and the overburdening of healthcare systems during the pandemic have compromised infection control measures, leading to increased transmission of these resistant pathogens within healthcare facilities (Samira et al., 2018)[213 (Aribisala & Sabiu, 2022)].

The results of the study will provide insights into the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance patterns among blood culture isolates in the tertiary care hospital. The data will be analyzed to identify any significant changes in the prevalence of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens during the pandemic period compared to the pre-pandemic, pandemic and post-pandemic periods. The study will focus on the resistance patterns of key pathogens such as *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus spp.*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*.

The findings will be presented in tables and figures to clearly illustrate the trends in antimicrobial resistance over the study:

Table 1:

Year	Acinetobacter sp.	Enterococcus sp.	Escherichia coli	Klebsiella pneumoniae ss. pneumoniae	Pseudomonas aeruginosa	Staphylococcus aureus ss. aureus
2019	97	46	53	54	20	93
2020	43	15	16	25	12	54
2021	26	38	8	40	17	87
2022	108	139	65	74	47	231
2023	268	341	81	150	172	255

Figure 1: Gram positive and Gram negative antimicrobial isolates as per NCDC resistance alert pathogens during period from July 2019 to December 2023

Gram positive cocci: The AMR Surveillance under NARS-Net covers 2 important globally prevalent gram-positive bacterial pathogens i.e. *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterococcus* species.

Staphylococcus aureus: The National Centre for Disease Control and the Indian Council of Medical Research has reported a high incidence of methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in healthcare settings in India (Santos et al., 2022). MRSA infections are associated with increased morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs.

According to the NCDC and ICMR, the prevalence of MRSA among *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates in India varies widely, ranging from 25% to 50%. The high rates of MRSA pose a significant challenge in

the management of *Staphylococcus aureus* infections.

According to the NCDC and ICMR, the prevalence of MRSA among *Staphylococcus aureus* isolates in India varies widely, ranging from 25% to 50%. The high rates of MRSA pose a significant challenge in the management of *Staphylococcus aureus* infections.

The increasing prevalence of MRSA is attributed to factors such as the indiscriminate use of antibiotics, poor infection control practices, and the spread of resistant strains within healthcare settings. (Santos et al., 2022) (Elmanama et al., 2013) (Srivastava et al., 2013) (Mehta et al., 2014)

Figure 2:

Enterococcus: According to the National Centre for Disease Control and the Indian Council of Medical Research, the increasing prevalence of antimicrobial resistance in Enterococcus is a major concern in India. Enterococcus species have developed resistance to a wide range of antibiotics, including vancomycin, which is often used as a last-resort treatment option.

Figure 3:

Pseudomonas aeruginosa: Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a highly adaptive and robust organism that can thrive in a wide range of environmental niches owing to its large and dynamic genome that provides extraordinary metabolic versatility and genetic plasticity (Amsalu et al., 2020).

The treatment of P. aeruginosa infections has become increasingly challenging due to the emergence and spread of antimicrobial resistance

(Kerr & Snelling, 2009). Resistance rates for P. aeruginosa were found to be high, with isolates showing significant resistance to commonly used antibiotics like piperacillin-tazobactam and carbapenems (Elmanama et al., 2013). The incidence of carbapenem-resistant P. aeruginosa has been increasing, posing a significant threat to the clinical management of infections caused by this pathogen (Kerr & Snelling, 2009) (Amsalu et al., 2020).

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

Escherichia coli & Klebsiella spp.:

The prevalence of multidrug-resistant, extensively drug-resistant, carbapenemase-producing, and carbapenem non-susceptible gram-negative bacteria was found to be alarmingly high in recent years (Horcajada et al., 2019) (Manik et al., 2023) (Abdeta et al., 2021). Specifically, the most frequently isolated XDR organisms were Klebsiella

pneumoniae, which accounted for a significant proportion of the gram-negative bacilli isolates in various studies.

The total resistance profile of Enterobacterales to extended-spectrum cephalosporins ranged from 57.7% to 80.8%, which was marginally higher than the findings of previous studies (Abdeta et al., 2021)

Figure 6:

Klebsiella spp.

Figure 7:

Acinetobacter Spp.:

The COVID-19 pandemic had led to an increase in the use of antibiotics, which is expected to contribute to the rise of antimicrobial resistance. Acinetobacter spp. is a major nosocomial pathogen that has demonstrated a concerning increase in multidrug resistance globally (Sunenshine et al., 2007). This study showed a significant increase in the proportion of Acinetobacter spp. isolates resistant to carbapenems, a commonly used class of antibiotics, during the COVID-19 pandemic period compared to the pre-pandemic period (Santos et al., 2022)(Fatema et al., 2016). The findings suggest that the increase in antibiotic usage during the COVID-19 pandemic may have accelerated the development and spread of antimicrobial resistance, particularly among Acinetobacter spp. (Santos et al., 2022) (Chowdhury & Uddin, 2022)

(Sunenshine et al., 2007) this is consistent with previous studies that have reported a rise in antimicrobial resistance in hospital settings during the pandemic. (Fatema et al., 2016)(Santos et al., 2022) The increased antibiotic usage is likely due to the empirical treatment of suspected secondary bacterial infections in COVID-19 patients, as well as the use of antibiotics to prevent such infections.

The study highlights the need for improved antimicrobial stewardship and infection control measures in healthcare settings, especially during public health emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic. A multidisciplinary approach involving clinicians, microbiologists, and public health experts is crucial to address the challenge of antimicrobial resistance and mitigate its impact on patient outcomes.

Figure 8:

Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the significant impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance patterns in a tertiary care hospital setting in North India. The increase in healthcare-associated infections and the rise in antimicrobial resistance, particularly among gram-negative bacteria, pose serious challenges to patient care and public health.

The observed trends in antimicrobial resistance, such as the increased prevalence of carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii*, are concerning and underscore the need for robust antimicrobial stewardship programs and strengthened infection control measures in healthcare settings. (Jiang et al., 2022)

The disruptions to routine healthcare services and resource constraints during the pandemic may have contributed to the suboptimal implementation of infection control practices, leading to the amplification of antimicrobial resistance. (Sands et al., 2023) Moreover, the increased use of antibiotics in the management of COVID-19 patients likely exerted considerable selection pressure, further driving the emergence and dissemination of resistant pathogens. (Wang & Wang, 2023)

To mitigate the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance, hospitals must prioritize the implementation of comprehensive infection control strategies, including enhanced hand hygiene, environmental cleaning, and the appropriate use of personal protective equipment. (Patel & Bonomo, 2013) (Towner, 2009)

Strengthening antimicrobial stewardship programs, which promote the judicious use of antibiotics, is also crucial to curb the rise of resistant pathogens. (Cohen, 1994)

The issue of antimicrobial resistance in India is particularly concerning, with high rates of resistance observed across various pathogens (Laxminarayan & Chaudhury, 2016). A mix of poor public health systems, high rates of infectious diseases, easy access to antibiotics, and rising incomes have contributed to the increasing prevalence of resistant pathogens (Laxminarayan & Chaudhury, 2016).

Studies have reported high levels of resistance among Gram-negative bacteria, such as *Escherichia coli*, which have shown resistance to commonly used antibiotics, including ampicillin, nalidixic acid, and co-trim oxazole (Laxminarayan & Chaudhury, 2016). Additionally, the emergence of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae, such as New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase-producing strains, has become a significant concern (Laxminarayan & Chaudhury, 2016).

The National Centre for Disease Control in India has played a crucial role in monitoring and addressing the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance. The NCDC has collaborated with key stakeholders, including the Indian Council of Medical Research, to develop guidelines and strategies to promote the appropriate use of antimicrobials during the pandemic.

One of the primary concerns raised by the NCDC is the increased use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, often empirically prescribed to COVID-19 patients,

which can contribute to the development of antimicrobial resistance. The NCDC has emphasized the importance of antimicrobial stewardship programs, which aim to optimize the use of antimicrobials and reduce the spread of resistant pathogens. The ICMR has also recognized the need to address this issue and has provided recommendations for the management of bacterial and fungal co-infections in COVID-19 patients

The World Health Organization has also played a crucial role in addressing the issue of antimicrobial resistance during the COVID-19 pandemic. The WHO has provided guidance on the appropriate use of antimicrobials in the context of COVID-19, emphasizing the need for healthcare facilities to implement antimicrobial stewardship programs and monitor the emergence of resistant pathogens (Haque, 2021).

Moreover, the WHO has called for a global effort to address the underlying drivers of antimicrobial resistance, such as the inappropriate use of antibiotics in human and animal health, as well as the environmental contamination of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria (White & Hughes, 2019). The organization has emphasized the importance of a "One Health" approach, which recognizes the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health in tackling the AMR crisis (Chandra et al., 2021).

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on antimicrobial resistance patterns in India. The prevalence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria has increased substantially during the pandemic, likely due to the widespread and often indiscriminate use of antibiotics in the treatment of COVID-19 patients. (Raghunath, 2008)(Laxminarayan & Chaudhury, 2016) This trend is particularly concerning given the already high rates of antibiotic resistance in the country. (Gandra et al., 2015) (Basak et al., 2016) The drivers of this phenomenon are multifaceted, involving a combination of poor public health systems, high rates of infectious disease, easy access to inexpensive antibiotics, and rising incomes. (Laxminarayan & Chaudhury, 2016) The emergence of new drug-resistant pathogens, such as the New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase enzymes, further exacerbates the situation. (Laxminarayan & Chaudhury, 2016).

To address this pressing issue, coordinated strategies involving key stakeholders, including the government, are crucial. (Haque, 2021) The National Centre for Disease Control in India can play a pivotal role in managing antimicrobial resistance by implementing the following measures:

Firstly, the NCDC should work to establish comprehensive surveillance systems to monitor the prevalence and patterns of antimicrobial resistance across the country. This data can then be used to inform the development of targeted interventions and policies to combat the issue. Secondly, the NCDC should collaborate with healthcare professionals, hospitals, and the general public to promote the responsible use of antibiotics through education and awareness campaigns. This 'One Health approach,' which considers the judicious use of antibiotics in humans, animals, and the environment, is crucial in stemming the tide of antimicrobial resistance.

Thirdly, the NCDC should work with the government to strengthen regulatory measures and enforcement of existing laws regarding the sale and use of antibiotics. This includes restricting the over-the-counter sale of antibiotics and ensuring that healthcare providers adhere to evidence-based prescribing guidelines.

Lastly, the NCDC should collaborate with the scientific community to support research and development of new antimicrobial agents and alternative treatment strategies.

By implementing these multifaceted approaches, the NCDC can play a critical role in addressing the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance in India, a crucial step in safeguarding the health and well-being of the population.

The Indian Council of Medical Research can also contribute significantly to the management of antimicrobial resistance in India. The ICMR can focus on the following key areas:

Firstly, the ICMR should establish a robust surveillance system to monitor the prevalence and patterns of antimicrobial resistance across the country. This data can then be used to inform the development of targeted interventions and policies to combat the issue.

Secondly, the ICMR should prioritize research and development of new antimicrobial agents and alternative treatment strategies to address the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance. This includes supporting the development of innovative diagnostic tools and therapies that can more effectively combat drug-resistant pathogens.

Thirdly, the ICMR should work to strengthen the capacity of healthcare institutions and providers to implement effective antimicrobial stewardship programs. These programs aim to promote the judicious use of antibiotics, reducing the emergence and spread of resistant bacteria.

Fourthly, the ICMR should collaborate with the government and other stakeholders to develop and implement comprehensive policies and regulations

to address the various drivers of antimicrobial resistance, such as the overuse and misuse of antibiotics in human and animal health sectors. By taking a multifaceted approach, the ICMR can play a crucial role in mitigating the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on antimicrobial resistance in India and safeguarding the long-term health and well-being of the population. (Chandra et al., 2021) (Miteu et al., 2023). The World Health Organization has developed a global strategy to address the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance. This strategy emphasizes the need for a "One Health" approach, which recognizes the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health in the development and spread of antimicrobial resistance. The key elements of the WHO's global strategy for AMR include:

Strengthening surveillance and research to expand the evidence base on antimicrobial resistance; Improving infection prevention and control measures to reduce the incidence of infections and the spread of antimicrobial resistance; Optimizing the use of antimicrobial agents through antimicrobial stewardship programs and policies; Investing in the research and development of new antimicrobial agents, alternative therapies, and diagnostic tools; and Fostering international cooperation and coordination to address the global nature of the antimicrobial resistance challenge. (Velázquez-Meza et al., 2022). By aligning with the WHO's global strategy, India can leverage the expertise and resources of the international community to bolster its own efforts to combat antimicrobial resistance.

The United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention has also provided recommendations for the management of antimicrobial resistance. Promoting the implementation of robust antimicrobial stewardship programs in healthcare settings, which aim to ensure the appropriate and judicious use of antibiotics. Enhancing surveillance and reporting of antimicrobial resistance patterns and trends, both at the national and local levels. Investing in the development of new antimicrobial agents, diagnostic tools, and alternative treatment strategies to address the growing challenge of drug-resistant pathogens. Implementing effective infection prevention and control measures, such as hand hygiene, environmental cleaning, and the use of personal protective equipment, to reduce the transmission of resistant bacteria.

Fostering collaboration and coordination among various stakeholders, including healthcare providers, policymakers, researchers, and the public, to develop and implement comprehensive strategies to combat antimicrobial resistance. (Miteu et al., 2023) (Velázquez-Meza et al., 2022).

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References

1. Abdeta, A., Bitew, A., Fentaw, S., Tsige, E., Assefa, D G., Lejisa, T., Kefyalew, Y., & Tigabu, E. (2021, August 17). Detection and phenotypic characterization of carbapenem non susceptible gram-negative bacilli isolated from clinical specimens. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.17.456671>
2. Amsalu, A., Sapula, S A., Lopes, M D B., Hart, B J., Nguyen, A H., Drigo, B., Turnidge, J., Leong, L., & Venter, H. (2020, October 24). Efflux Pump-Driven Antibiotic and Biocide Cross-Resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Isolated from Different Ecological Niches: A Case Study in the Development of Multidrug Resistance in Environmental Hotspots. *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute*, 8(11), 1647-1647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms8111647>
3. Arentz, M., Ma, J., Zheng, P., Vos, T., Murray, C J L., & Kyu, H H. (2022, January 27). The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and associated suppression measures on the burden of tuberculosis in India. *BioMed Central*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-022-07078-y>
4. Aribisala, O., & Sabiu, S. (2022, August 29). Cheminformatics Identification of Phenolics as Modulators of Penicillin-Binding Protein 2a of *Staphylococcus aureus*: A Structure-Activity-Relationship-Based Study. *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute*, 14(9), 1818-1818. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics14091818>
5. Basak, S., Singh, P., & Rajurkar, M. (2016, January 1). Multidrug Resistant and Extensively Drug Resistant Bacteria: A Study. *Hindawi Publishing Corporation*, 2016, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/4065603>
6. Bogdan, I., Gadela, T., Bratosin, F., Dumitru, C., Popescu, A., Horhat, F G., Negrean, R A., Horhat, R M., Moț, I C., Bota, A V., Stoica, C N., Feciche, B., Nicolae, A., Fericean, R M., Chicin, G N., & Marincu, I. (2023, February 24). The Assessment of Multiplex PCR in Identifying Bacterial Infections in Patients Hospitalized with SARS-CoV-2 Infection: A Systematic Review. *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute*, 12(3), 465-465. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics12030465>
7. Chandra, P., Unnikrishnan, M K., Eshwara, V K., Mukhopadhyay, C., Acharya, U D., Mallayasamy, S., & Rajesh, V. (2021, July 22).

- Antimicrobial resistance and the post antibiotic era: better late than never effort. Taylor & Francis, 20(11), 1375-1390. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14740338.2021.1928633>
8. Chandra, P., Unnikrishnan, M K., Eshwara, V K., Mukhopadhyay, C., Acharya, U D., Malayasamy, S., & Rajesh, V. (2021, July 22). Antimicrobial resistance and the post antibiotic era: better late than never effort. Taylor & Francis, 20(11), 1375-1390. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14740338.2021.1928633>
 9. Chowdhury, A M M A., & Uddin, K N. (2022, January 1). Analysis of the Occurrence of Antibiotic Resistant Bacteria in the Hospital's Effluent and its Receiving Environment. SAGE Publishing, 15, 117863612210782-117863612210782. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11786361221078211>
 10. Elmanama, A A., Laham, N A., & Tayh, G. (2013, December 1). Antimicrobial susceptibility of bacterial isolates from burn units in Gaza. Elsevier BV, 39(8), 1612-1618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.burns.2013.04.011>
 11. Fatema, K., Ahsan, A A., Barai, L., Ahmed, F., Haq, J A., & Faruq, M O. (2016, October 21). Bacterial profile and their antibiotic resistance in an ICU of Bangladesh: Comparison of four studies from 2004 to 2011. , 4(2), 79-85. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bccj.v4i2.30021>
 12. Gandra, S., Mojica, N., Ashok, A., Das, B., & Laxminarayan, R. (2015, June 16). Trends in antibiotic resistance among bacteria isolated from blood cultures using a large private laboratory network data in India: 2008-2014. BioMed Central, 4(S1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/2047-2994-4-s1-o42>
 13. Goto, M., McDanel, J S., Jones, M., Livorsi, D., Ohl, M., Beck, B., Richardson, K., Alexander, B., & Perencevich, E N. (2017, November 1). Antimicrobial Nonsusceptibility of Gram-Negative Bloodstream Isolates, Veterans Health Administration System, United States, 2003–20131. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 23(11), 1815-1825. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid2311.161214>
 14. Hang, N T T., Venter, H., Woolford, L., Young, K A., McCluskey, A., Garg, S., Page, S W., Trott, D J., & Ogunniyi, A D. (2022, January 6). Impact of a Novel Anticoccidial Analogue on Systemic Staphylococcus aureus Infection in a Bioluminescent Mouse Model. Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, 11(1), 65-65. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics11010065>
 15. Haque, M. (2021, January 1). Potential ways to address antimicrobial resistance across India and wider exacerbated by COVID-19. Open Science Publishers LLP. <https://doi.org/10.7324/japs.2021.11010ed>
 16. Haque, M. (2021, January 1). Potential ways to address antimicrobial resistance across India and wider exacerbated by COVID-19. Open Science Publishers LLP. <https://doi.org/10.7324/japs.2021.11010ed>
 17. Horcajada, J P., Montero, M., Oliver, A., Sorlí, L., Luque, S., Gómez-Zorrilla, S., Benito, N., & Grau, S. (2019, September 18). Epidemiology and Treatment of Multidrug-Resistant and Extensively Drug-Resistant Pseudomonas aeruginosa Infections. American Society for Microbiology, 32(4). <https://doi.org/10.1128/cmr.00031-19>
 18. Kerr, K., & Snelling, A. (2009, December 1). Pseudomonas aeruginosa: a formidable and ever-present adversary. Elsevier BV, 73(4), 338-344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhin.2009.04.020>
 19. Khan, A., Chakravarty, A., & Mahapatra, J. (2021, January 1). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on childhood immunization in a Tertiary Health-Care Center. Medknow, 46(3), 520-520. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijcm.ijcm_847_20
 20. Laxminarayan, R., & Chaudhury, R R. (2016, March 2). Antibiotic Resistance in India: Drivers and Opportunities for Action. Public Library of Science, 13(3), e1001974-e1001974. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1001974>
 21. Manik, R K., Mahmud, Z., Mishu, I D., Hossen, M S., Howlader, Z H., & Nabi, A N. (2023, August 5). Multidrug Resistance Profiles and Resistance Mechanisms to β -Lactams and Fluoroquinolones in Bacterial Isolates from Hospital Wastewater in Bangladesh. Caister Academic Press, 45(8), 6485-6502. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cimb45080409>
 22. McEwen, S A., & Collignon, P. (2018, April 6). Antimicrobial Resistance: a One Health Perspective. American Society for Microbiology, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.1128/microbio-spec.arba-0009-2017>
 23. Mehta, S., Sahni, N G A K., Singh, V A., Bungler, R., Garg, T., & Shinu, P. (2014, May 14). Nosocomial Wound Infection amongst Post-Operative Patients and their Antibio-grams at Tertiary Care Hospital in India. African Journals OnLine, 15(2), 60-60. <https://doi.org/10.4314/ajcem.v15i2.2>
 24. Michael, C A., Dominey-Howes, D., & Labbate, M. (2014, September 16). The Antimicrobial Resistance Crisis: Causes, Consequences, and Management. Frontiers Media, 2. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2014.00145>
 25. Miteu, G D., Achinebiri, P., Raghunathan, N., & Sankaran, S. (2023, May 3). Closing potential drivers of antimicrobial resistance: last-resort antimicrobials with the potential of being misused, the way forward – a short communication. Elsevier BV, 85(6), 3226-3231.

- <https://doi.org/10.1097/ms9.0000000000000760>
26. Murthy, R. (2001, February 1). Implementation of Strategies to Control Antimicrobial Resistance. Elsevier BV, 119(2), 405S-411S. https://doi.org/10.1378/chest.119.2_suppl.405s
 27. Pandey, R., Mishra, S K., & Shrestha, A. (2021, June 1). Characterisation of ESKAPE Pathogens with Special Reference to Multi-drug Resistance and Biofilm Production in a Nepalese Hospital. Dove Medical Press, Volume 14, 2201-2212. <https://doi.org/10.2147/idr.s306688>
 28. Papamanoli, A., Yoo, J., Mojahedi, A., Jacob, R G., Grewal, P., Dhaliwal, S., Coritsidis, A., Nakamura, J., Fung, J N., Hotelling, J., Rawal, S., Karkala, N., Tsui, S T., Abata, J., Pseudos, G., Kalogeropoulos, A P., & Marcos, L A. (2020, October 1). 53. Incidence of Bloodstream Infections and Outcomes in Patients with Severe COVID-19 Pneumonia. Oxford University Press, 7(Supplement 1), S156-S157. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ofid/ofaa439.363>
 29. Papamanoli, A., Yoo, J., Mojahedi, A., Jacob, R G., Grewal, P., Dhaliwal, S., Coritsidis, A., Nakamura, J., Fung, J N., Hotelling, J., Rawal, S., Karkala, N., Tsui, S T., Abata, J., Pseudos, G., Kalogeropoulos, A P., & Marcos, L A. (2020, October 1). 53. Incidence of Bloodstream Infections and Outcomes in Patients with Severe COVID-19 Pneumonia. Oxford University Press, 7(Supplement 1), S156-S157. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ofid/ofaa439.363>
 30. Patel, I., Hussain, R., Khan, A., Ahmad, A., Khan, M U., & Hassalal, M A A. (2017, September 5). Antimicrobial resistance in India. BioMed Central, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-017-0118-6>
 31. Qian, Y., Zhou, D., Li, M., Zhao, Y., Liu, H., Li, Y., Ying, Z., & Huang, G. (2023, August 17). Application of CRISPR-Cas system in the diagnosis and therapy of ESKAPE infections. Frontiers Media, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcimb.2023.1223696>
 32. Raghunath, D. (2008, November 1). Emerging antibiotic resistance in bacteria with special reference to India. Springer Science+Business Media, 33(4), 593-603. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12038-008-0077-9>
 33. Rosa, T F D., Coelho, S S., Foletto, V S., Bottega, A., Serafin, M B., Machado, C D S., Franco, L N., Paula, B R D., & Hörner, R. (2020, April 27). Alternatives for the treatment of infections caused by ESKAPE pathogens. Wiley, 45(4), 863-873. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcpt.13149>
 34. Samira, A., Ahmed, S., & Meundi, M. (2018, February 10). Staphylococcus aureus – A Versatile Pathogen Biochemical Characterization and Antibiogram. Excellent Publishers, 7(2), 2933-2941. <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijcmas.2018.702.356>
 35. Sands, K., Blanchard, E J., Fraker, S., Korwek, K., & Cuffe, M S. (2023, April 13). Health Care–Associated Infections Among Hospitalized Patients With COVID-19, March 2020–March 2022. American Medical Association, 6(4), e238059-e238059. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2023.8059>
 36. Santos, J V D O., Júnior, S D D C., Medeiros, S M D F R D S., Cavalcanti, I D L., Souza, J B D., Coriolano, D D L., Silva, W R C D., Alves, M H M E., & Cavalcanti, I M F. (2022, April 30). Panorama of Bacterial Infections Caused by Epidemic Resistant Strains. Springer Science+Business Media, 79(6). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00284-022-02875-9>
 37. Srivastava, J., Chandra, H., Nautiyal, A R., & Kalra, S J S. (2013, October 23). Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and plant-derived antimicrobials (PDAMs) as an alternative drug line to control infections. Springer Science+Business Media, 4(5), 451-460. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-013-0180-y>
 38. Sunenshine, R., Wright, M., Maragakis, L L., Harris, A., Song, X., Hebden, J., Cosgrove, S E., Anderson, A., Carnell, J., Jernigan, D B., Kleinbaum, D G., Perl, T M., Standiford, H C., & Srinivasan, A. (2007, January 1). Multidrug-resistant Acinetobacter Infection Mortality Rate and Length of Hospitalization. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 13(1), 97-103. <https://doi.org/10.3201/eid1301.060716>
 39. Velázquez-Meza, M E., Galarde-López, M., Carrillo-Quiroz, B A., & Alpuche-Aranda, C. (2022, March 28). Antimicrobial resistance: One Health approach. Veterinary World, 743-749. <https://doi.org/10.14202/vetworld.2022.743-749>
 40. Wang, L., & Wang, L. (2023, April 2). Hospital X's Effective Strategy in Improving Patient Safety in the Era of the COVID-19 Pandemic, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.30604/jika.v8i2.1866>
 41. White, A M., & Hughes, J M. (2019, June 28). Critical Importance of a One Health Approach to Antimicrobial Resistance. Springer Science+Business Media, 16(3), 404-409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10393-019-01415-5>